

Parasitization of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers in the Philippines. ^aIRRI, 1985-86.

Host	Specimen dissected (no.)	Parasitization (%)				
		<i>Halictophagus</i>			<i>Elenchus</i>	
		<i>spectrus</i>	<i>munroei</i>	<i>bipunctatus</i> ^b	<i>yasumatsui</i>	? <i>japonicus</i> ^b
Cicadellidae						
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	1884	—	0.1	0.3	—	—
<i>N. nigropictus</i> (Stal)	3621	—	—	0.1	—	—
<i>Cofana spectra</i> (Distant)	1875	10	—	—	—	—
Delphacidae						
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stal)	4666	—	—	—	9	—
<i>N. bakeri</i> (Muir) ^b	430	—	—	—	0.7	—
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	5045	—	—	—	2.1	8
<i>S. longifurcifera</i> (Esaki & Ishihara)	238	—	—	—	—	3.4
<i>S. kolophon</i> (Kirkaldy)	175	—	—	—	—	1.1
<i>Sogatodes pusanus</i> (Distant)	5730	—	—	—	3.2	11

^a *H. piperi* and its host *C. longa* were not collected. ^b New records.

virescens and *N. nigropictus*. *E. nr. japonicus* Esaki et Hashimoto was taken from the whitebacked planthopper complex *Sogatella* and *Sogatodes*.

Parasitization by strepsiptera is low, 0.1-11%, but supplements that of other nymphal-adult parasites, such as *Tomosvaryella* and *Pipunculus*, in regulating populations of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. Strepsipterans cause castration or stylopization on the host genitalia. Usually they occur as wormlike or pupiform structures with their cephalothorax exerted between the dorsal or ventral abdominal segments of hoppers. An infested host usually has two to three adult strepsiptera embedded in its abdomen.

***Nymphula africalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), a pest of azolla in Nigeria**

M.S. Alam, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Oyo Road, PMB 5320, Ibadan, Nigeria

In China, six moths, one beetle, and a snail are considered major pests of azolla. Information on insect pests of azolla in Africa is scarce. In West Africa, two pests (snail *Limnea natalensis* and caseworm *Nymphula* sp.)

are reported to have quickly destroyed the inoculum of *Azolla pinnata* var. *africana*.

In Sep-Oct 1986, azolla in an irrigated ricefield at Ibadan was infested with caseworm *Nymphula africalis* Hampson. The adult *N. africalis* is a dull-colored moth about 10 mm long with 4 distinct wavy bands on its forewings and a 15- to 18-mm wing span (Fig. 1). Newly hatched larvae feed on azolla leaf buds.

After a few days, they conceal themselves in cases made from azolla

1. Adult moth of *Nymphula africalis*.

2. a) Larval case, b) full-grown larva, and c) pupal case of *Nymphula africalis*.

fronds, which they carry with them as they move about for food. Larvae stretch their heads and thoraxes from the cases to feed. A full-grown larva is 15-16 mm long and will consume 9-14 azolla leaves a day.

The larval cases are about 20 mm long. Mature larvae spin cocoons inside the cases for pupation. A pupal case is about 14 mm long (Fig. 2). Pupae are brown and about 9 mm long. Adult moths emerge from cocoons within a week.